

Isomerisation of α -Pinene to Camphene

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Manuscript received 19 February 1974; revised 26 August 1974; accepted 23 September 1974

An active catalyst for the isomerisation of α -pinene to camphene has been developed from Indian Kaolin. This simple preparative method gives a catalyst of reproducible activity. A detailed study of the reaction conditions has helped to find out the optimum conditions resulting in a 70% conversion.

IN the preparation of camphor from α -pinene, the isomerisation step involving the conversion of α -pinene to camphene is the most crucial and difficult step. Success of a commercial production much depends on this very step. Intensive investigations¹⁻⁷ have been carried on catalytic isomerisation by a number of workers and many patents⁸⁻¹⁶ have been taken claiming a yield as high as 70-80%. But in most cases except a few^{1,4} neither the details for the preparation of catalyst nor the reaction conditions are available for their commercial exploitations. Efforts have been made by the present authors to bridge this gap and the findings are reported in this article.

Based on earlier reports a number of catalysts have been prepared from titanium dioxide, kaolin, boric acid, silicic acid, salicylic acid amongst which the maximum conversion has been obtained with kaolin catalyst. In a comparative study involving different grades of kaolin, the technical grade has been found to be most satisfactory. Kaolin catalysts with different pH values were prepared by dialysis in a parchment bag and a subsequent study with them has shown the particular catalyst with pH 2.9 to be the most suitable one. On the other hand, catalysts dried either in vacuum or in an air oven seems to have no observable effect on the isomerisation process. Besides this, investigations have been carried on the effects of catalyst concentrations, reaction time and temperature. The optimum catalyst concentration, reaction time and temperature have been found to be 2% w/w, 2 hrs and 115°-120° respectively. There are evidences for the use of some inorganic salts like magnesium sulfate, potassium bisulfate as promoters in the isomerisation reaction. A detailed investigation on this aspect has shown that the use of potassium bisulfate in traces at the end of a period of 2 hr. of reaction and its continuation for another $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. increases the yield by nearly 10%. Camphene was estimated at various stages of the reaction by the methods¹⁷⁻¹⁸ earlier reported by the present authors and was finally isolated by careful fractional distillation.

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Experimental

Chemicals and Reagents : α -Pinene, processed from Indian turpentine oil (*P. longifolia*), was supplied by S. H. Kelkar and Co., Bombay; b.p. 155°-157°. d_{40}^{30} 0.8551, n_D^{25} 1.4646, $(\alpha)_D^{25}$ 40.30. Technical grade kaolin was supplied by Indian Mineral Industries (P) Ltd., Dum Dum, Calcutta. Hydrochloric acid (C.P.) and potassium bisulfate (A.R., BDH) were used.

Preparation of Catalyst :

Technical grade kaolin (12.5 g.), collected by size separation through a 60 mesh sieve, was suspended in water (50 ml.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (25 ml.) was added to it. The whole mass was refluxed for 6 hrs. and left overnight. It was then washed with water by centrifuging and subsequent decantation till it attained the pH 2.9. The catalyst was dried in a hot air oven at 120° for 4-6 hrs. and then stored in a vacuum desiccator. Compositions of kaolin and the prepared catalyst in percent are given below :

	Kaolin	Catalyst
SiO ₂	46.40	51.82
Al ₂ O ₃	37.62	33.11
Fe ₂ O ₃	2.28	1.32
CaO	0.76	0.38
MgO	0.09	0.06
H ₂ O	12.84	13.30

Isomerisation :

A 100 ml three necked flask fitted with a reflux condenser, a magnetic stirrer and a thermometer was placed on an oil bath and air inside the apparatus was replaced with a current of carbon dioxide. Freshly distilled α -pinene (20 g.) was introduced in the flask and heated at 115°-120° when the catalyst (0.4 g.) was added to it in small portions under stirring. Heating and stirring was continued for 2 hrs. Traces of potassium bisulfate (50 mg.) was added and the

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reaction was continued for another $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. After the reaction was over the whole mass was cooled, the catalyst was separated either by filtration or centrifuging and finally camphene was isolated by fractional distillation at 110° – $112^{\circ}/18$ mm. in 70% yield (14 g.).

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